

Refractive indices of formamide + alkanol/alkanediol binary mixtures at different temperatures

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Abstract : The refractive indices (n) of pure formamide (FA), ethanol, 1-propanol, 1,2-ethanediol, 1,2-propanediol and those of their forty four binary mixtures, with FA as common component, covering the whole composition range have been measured at 293.15, 298.15, 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K. The deviation in refractive index (Δn) has been calculated from the experimental data. The variation of Δn with composition and temperature of the mixtures have been discussed in terms of molecular interaction in these mixtures. It is observed that the extent of deviation in Δn for these mixtures follows the sequence : ethanol > 1-propanol > 1,2-ethanediol > 1,2-propanediol, indicating the presence of strong interactions in these mixtures in the same order.

Keywords : Refractive index, formamide, alkanol, alkanediol, molecular interactions.

Introduction

In continuation of our earlier studies, we report here the results of our studies on refractive indices of the binary mixtures of formamide (FA) with ethanol, 1-propanol, 1,2-ethanediol and 1,2-propanediol, over the entire composition range at six different temperatures¹. FA molecules are highly polar having dipole moment, $\mu = 3.37$ D at 298.15 K and are strongly self-associated through network of hydrogen bonds². Alkanol molecules are polar and self-associated through hydrogen bonding of their hydroxyl groups, whereas alkanediol molecules are self-associated through inter- and intra-molecular hydrogen bonding. Since the components of these binary mixtures (FA and alkanols) have both proton-donating as well as

proton-accepting abilities, significant interaction through hydrogen bonding between unlike molecules in these binary systems is expected. The experimental values of n have been used to calculate the deviations in refractive index, Δn and the results were discussed in terms of molecular interactions in these mixtures.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of refractive index, n of the binary mixtures of formamide (FA) with ethanol, 1-propanol, 1,2-ethanediol and 1,2-propanediol as a function of mole fraction, x_1 of FA at different temperatures are listed in Table 1. The deviations in refractive index, Δn

Table 1. Values of refractive index, n as function of mole fraction, x_1 of FA for the binary mixtures at different temperatures

x_1	T (K)					
	293.15	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15	318.15
	FA + ethanol					
0.0000	1.3616	1.3595	1.3573	1.3552	1.3530	1.3508
0.0698	1.3665	1.3646	1.3626	1.3607	1.3588	1.3569
0.1412	1.3719	1.3701	1.3683	1.3665	1.3647	1.3629
0.2032	1.3768	1.3752	1.3734	1.3717	1.3699	1.3681
0.2680	1.3819	1.3803	1.3787	1.3770	1.3753	1.3736

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

0.3874	1.3912	1.3897	1.3882	1.3867	1.3851	1.3836
0.4962	1.4001	1.3987	1.3973	1.3959	1.3945	1.3931
0.5958	1.4086	1.4074	1.4061	1.4048	1.4035	1.4022
0.7080	1.4186	1.4175	1.4164	1.4153	1.4142	1.4130
0.7748	1.4247	1.4237	1.4227	1.4217	1.4207	1.4197
0.8532	1.4322	1.4313	1.4304	1.4295	1.4286	1.4277
0.9282	1.4398	1.4390	1.4381	1.4373	1.4365	1.4356
1.0000	1.4475	1.4467	1.4459	1.4451	1.4442	1.4433
FA + 1-propanol						
0.0000	1.3855	1.3836	1.3817	1.3799	1.3781	1.3763
0.0557	1.3879	1.3861	1.3843	1.3826	1.3809	1.3792
0.1172	1.3905	1.3888	1.3871	1.3855	1.3838	1.3822
0.1854	1.3934	1.3918	1.3902	1.3887	1.3871	1.3855
0.2615	1.3969	1.3953	1.3938	1.3923	1.3907	1.3892
0.3469	1.4010	1.3995	1.3980	1.3966	1.3951	1.3936
0.4434	1.4059	1.4045	1.4031	1.4017	1.4003	1.3989
0.5534	1.4121	1.4108	1.4095	1.4082	1.4069	1.4056
0.6800	1.4202	1.4190	1.4178	1.4167	1.4155	1.4143
0.8270	1.4312	1.4302	1.4292	1.4282	1.4271	1.4261
0.8832	1.4360	1.4351	1.4342	1.4332	1.4323	1.4313
0.9328	1.4406	1.4398	1.4389	1.4380	1.4371	1.4362
1.0000	1.4475	1.4467	1.4459	1.4451	1.4442	1.4433
FA + 1,2-ethanediol						
0.0000	1.4319	1.4307	1.4296	1.4284	1.4272	1.4260
0.0612	1.4324	1.4312	1.4301	1.4289	1.4277	1.4265
0.1204	1.4329	1.4317	1.4306	1.4294	1.4282	1.4270
0.1859	1.4336	1.4324	1.4313	1.4302	1.4290	1.4278
0.3302	1.4354	1.4343	1.4332	1.4321	1.4309	1.4298
0.4517	1.4371	1.4360	1.4350	1.4339	1.4328	1.4316
0.5643	1.4388	1.4378	1.4368	1.4358	1.4347	1.4336
0.6596	1.4404	1.4394	1.4385	1.4375	1.4364	1.4353
0.7454	1.4420	1.4410	1.4401	1.4391	1.4381	1.4371
0.8195	1.4435	1.4425	1.4416	1.4407	1.4397	1.4387
0.8883	1.4449	1.4440	1.4431	1.4423	1.4413	1.4403
0.9491	1.4463	1.4454	1.4446	1.4438	1.4428	1.4419
1.0000	1.4475	1.4467	1.4459	1.4451	1.4442	1.4433
FA + 1,2-propanediol						
0.0000	1.4329	1.4314	1.4299	1.4284	1.4269	1.4256
0.0567	1.4328	1.4313	1.4298	1.4283	1.4267	1.4254
0.1191	1.4329	1.4314	1.4299	1.4284	1.4268	1.4255
0.1881	1.4332	1.4317	1.4302	1.4287	1.4272	1.4259
0.2649	1.4337	1.4323	1.4308	1.4293	1.4279	1.4266
0.3409	1.4344	1.4330	1.4316	1.4301	1.4287	1.4274
0.4478	1.4355	1.4342	1.4329	1.4315	1.4301	1.4289
0.5578	1.4370	1.4358	1.4345	1.4333	1.4319	1.4307
0.6838	1.4392	1.4381	1.4369	1.4357	1.4345	1.4333

Table-1 (contd.)

0.8295	1.4424	1.4414	1.4404	1.4393	1.4382	1.4371
0.8818	1.4438	1.4429	1.4419	1.4409	1.4398	1.4388
0.9392	1.4455	1.4447	1.4437	1.4428	1.4418	1.4408
1.0000	1.4474	1.4467	1.4459	1.4451	1.4442	1.4433

have been calculated by using the following relation,

$$\Delta n = n - (\phi_1 n_1 + \phi_2 n_2) \quad (1)$$

where ϕ is the volume fraction (calculated using the molar volumes of the pure components obtained from the density data from our earlier work³) and the subscripts 1 and 2 represent pure components, FA and alkanol, respectively. The values of Δn were fitted to a Redlich-Kister type polynomial equation of the form⁴

$$\Delta n = \phi_1(1 - \phi_1) \sum_{i=1}^5 A_i(1 - 2\phi_1)^{i-1} \quad (2)$$

The values of coefficients, A_i evaluated by the method of least-squares, with all points weighted equally, together with the corresponding standard deviation, σ calculated by using the relation,

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{\sum (\Delta n_{\text{Expt.}} - \Delta n_{\text{Calcd.}})^2}{(m - k)} \right]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

where m is the number of experimental data points and k is the number of coefficients considered ($k = 5$ in the present calculation), are listed in Table 2. The values of

Table 2. Coefficients, A_i of eq. (2) of Δn (10^{-2}) and standard deviations, σ for FA + alkanol mixtures at different temperatures

T (K)	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	σ (10^{-2})
FA + ethanol						
293.15	1.5836	0.5468	0.3991	-0.0858	-0.8392	0.0083
298.15	1.6665	0.5303	0.4735	0.0109	-0.6942	0.0106
303.15	1.7513	0.5499	0.7226	0.1929	-0.9495	0.0091
308.15	1.8224	0.5351	0.7797	0.2630	-0.7769	0.0077
313.15	1.9370	0.4746	0.6947	0.3845	-0.2435	0.0062
318.15	2.0409	0.4648	1.7720	0.4872	-0.0543	0.0032
FA + 1-propanol						
293.15	0.7568	0.3607	0.1112	0.2972	0.2028	0.0031
298.15	0.8125	0.3833	0.1425	0.3255	0.3386	0.0029
303.15	0.8639	0.4073	0.2417	0.3858	0.3971	0.0025
308.15	0.9232	0.3875	0.1243	0.5977	0.6589	0.0011
313.15	0.9766	0.4175	0.1111	0.5108	0.8132	0.0033
318.15	1.0331	0.3920	0.1216	0.5826	0.9806	0.0031
FA + 1,2-ethanediol						
293.15	-0.2218	-0.0595	-0.0847	-0.1356	-0.1385	0.0006
298.15	-0.2383	-0.0656	-0.0972	-0.1451	-0.1452	0.0008
303.15	-0.2542	-0.0663	-0.1095	-0.1519	-0.1452	0.0008
308.15	-0.2661	-0.0693	-0.1205	-0.1517	-0.1755	0.0009
313.15	-0.2847	-0.0748	-0.1172	-0.1587	-0.2016	0.0006
318.15	-0.3002	-0.0733	-0.1046	-0.1566	-0.2518	0.0006
FA + 1,2-propanediol						
293.15	-0.6472	-0.3685	-0.1715	-0.3917	-0.3363	0.0020
298.15	-0.6709	-0.3443	-0.1977	-0.4471	-0.3832	0.0019
303.15	-0.6894	-0.3503	-0.2618	-0.4441	-0.4289	0.0015
308.15	-0.7199	-0.3242	-0.2708	-0.5540	-0.4896	0.0020
313.15	-0.7507	-0.2999	-0.2335	-0.6378	-0.6410	0.0028
318.15	-0.7806	-0.3073	-0.2293	-0.6404	-0.7626	0.0035

$\Delta n_{\text{Calcd.}}$ were obtained from eq. (2) by using the best-fit values of coefficient A_i . The variations of Δn with composition (in terms of mole fraction) of the mixture along with smoothed Δn values by using the eq. (2), at 298.15 and 318.15 K are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Plots of deviations in refractive index, Δn vs mole fraction, x_1 of formamide (FA) for the binary mixtures at (a) 298.15 K and (b) 318.15 K. The points show experimental values and curves show smoothed values using eq. (2).

Fig. 1 indicates that Δn values are positive over entire composition range and at all temperatures investigated for FA + ethanol/1-propanol, and are negative for FA +

1,2-ethanediol/1,2-propanediol. The extent of deviation in Δn from linear dependence on composition follows the sequence : ethanol > 1-propanol > 1,2-ethanediol > 1,2-propanediol. The observed trends (Fig. 1) and magnitudes of Δn values indicate the presence of strong interactions in FA + ethanol/1-propanol mixtures, whereas weak interactions in FA + 1,2-ethanediol/1,2-propanediol mixtures, which follow the order : ethanol > 1-propanol > 1,2-ethanediol > 1,2-propanediol. The Δn values decrease with increase in temperature for all the four binary mixtures, indicating that the interactions between unlike molecules decrease with rise in temperature. This further supports our earlier conclusions regarding formamide-alkanol or alkanediol interactions in these mixtures from the variations of V_m^E values³ with composition and temperature. Also, the deviations in Δn values are opposite to the sign of excess molar volumes V_m^E for all the four binary mixtures³, in agreement with earlier observations⁵.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the study were the products from s.d. fine-Chem. Ltd. (India) and were purified by standard methods⁶. The mixtures were prepared by mass using an electronic balance with a precision of ± 0.1 mg.

The refractive indices of pure liquids and their binary mixtures were measured with a thermostated Abbe refractometer. The refractometer was calibrated by measuring the refractive indices of triply distilled water and toluene at sodium D light at the desired temperatures. The reproducibility of refractive index measurements was within ± 0.0001 . The reliability of experimental measurements of n was ascertained by comparing the experimental data of pure liquids with the corresponding values available in the literature at 298.15 K⁶.

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